

A Review on the Occurrence and Impacts of Nutrient Pollution in the Aquatic Ecosystem of Sub-Saharan Countries

Asha Ripanda^{*1}, Hossein Miraji²

¹*Department of Chemistry, College of Natural and Mathematical Sciences, University of Dodoma, Dodoma, Tanzania*

²*Department of Chemistry, College of Natural and Mathematical Sciences, University of Dodoma, Dodoma, Tanzania*

Article published on January 12, 2022

Key words: Emerging contaminants, Nutrient pollution, East Africa, Ecosystem health, Nitrate, Phosphate

Abstract

Nutrient pollution significantly threatens ecosystem health globally and is aggravated by anthropogenic activities. In this case, algae grow faster than the ecosystem can handle. Apart from other reported effects, some algae blooms are toxic and produce toxins, leading to the deterioration of ecosystem health. These blooms are becoming prevalent, hence the possibility of increased diseases to the entire ecosystem and unsustainability. In many parts of the world, nutrient contamination poses a significant hazard to human health and the ecosystem. Effects of excessive nutrients in the environment include excessive growth of algae. Apart from the difficulties of handling excess nitrogen in the air that make it difficult to breathe, reduce visibility, affect plant growth, a recently reported altering the gut microbiome of a territorial reef fish. Therefore, the present study aimed to assess the nutrient (nitrate and phosphate) contamination in the Sub-Saharan African environment in various matrices including water, groundwater, wastewater, soil, sediments and surface waters to inform policy. In this case, this study investigates the status of nutrient pollution in Sub Saharan Africa, the potential source of nutrient pollution, the reported effects of nutrient pollution; How to overcome nutrient pollution in the environment. Among the measures recommended for nutrient, pollution management includes decreased use of fertilizers and pesticides or organic farming and considerations during the choice of detergents, soaps and household cleaners to nutrient-free products for environmental conservation.

*Corresponding Author: Asha Ripanda ✉ asha.ripanda@udom.ac.tz

Introduction

Nutrients are chemicals that are required for organisms and ecosystems to function correctly. While ecological productivity may be distorted (Orlans and Milewski, 2007), its excessiveness results in toxicity that may harm the environment (Shaviv and Mikkelsen, 1993). Nitrogen and phosphorus are nutrients that are natural parts of aquatic ecosystems. Nitrogen is also the most abundant element in the air we breathe. Nitrogen and phosphorus support the growth of algae and aquatic plants, which provide food and habitat for fish, shellfish and smaller organisms that live in water (Selman and Greenhalgh, 2010). Excessive nitrogen and phosphorus in the water can have a wide range of health, environmental, and economic consequences, therefore referred to as nutrient pollution (Leip *et al.*, 2015, Sanseverino *et al.*, 2016). Researchers reported nitrate and phosphate could pose a significant threat to freshwater macroinvertebrates when released into the aquatic environment without being treated (Camargo and Ward, 1992, Camargo and Ward, 1995).

Apart from established tolerance thresholds of various taxa towards organic pollution gradients, reports of freshwater macroinvertebrates in tropical African regions response to high nitrate and phosphate levels is lacking (Camargo and Alonso, 2006, Assessment, 2003). In freshwater ecosystems, sensitive macroinvertebrate groups may be driven to extinction by elevated nitrate and phosphate levels (Camargo *et al.*, 2005). Severe impacts of nutrient pollution from developed countries are available, such as the United States of America and China have reported an unsustainable ecosystem as a result of nutrient pollution (Lapointe *et al.*, 2017, Kuwayama *et al.*, 2020, Chen *et al.*, 2019, Chadwick *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, authorities in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) must initiate early measures to protect the environment from nutrient pollution. This study reviews literature on nutrient pollution that was peer-reviewed and published in academic journals, conference papers, books, book chapters, and reports. The primary search was between August and October, 2021. The area and the scope of this

literature review were nutrient pollution and its effects in Sub Saharan Africa.

A study by Peng and colleagues looked into the consequences of air pollution, water pollution, and their spillover effects on health (Peng *et al.*, 2021). The Spatial Durbin Model revealed that for every 1 ton per capita per year rise in the average amount of soot/dust released by its nearby provinces, a province's ill-health score increased by 6.649. On the other hand, a province's ill-health score increased by 0.004 for every 1 ton per capita increase in wastewater released per year. Indicating that nutrient pollution contributes to the deterioration of ecosystem health and, therefore, may lead to unsustainable ecosystems if not adequately mitigated (Council, 1992, Chadwick *et al.*, 2020). While some coastal waters may benefit from moderate nutrient enrichment, over-enrichment disrupts the marine food chain, sustaining commercially valuable species. Nutrient pollution is a significant concern worldwide. Coastal waters, bays, streams, lakes, and rivers have claimed polluted for decades, resulting in an unhealthy ecosystem. As a result, it is critical to investigate and report nutrient pollution in SSA countries to take the required steps to ensure environmental sustainability. This study looks into the current state of nutrient pollution in SSA's aquatic ecosystems and how it affects ecosystem health.

Integrated nutrients cycle

The nutrition cycle outlines how nutrients are transferred from the physical environment to living creatures and returned to the physical environment (Daily, 2003, Bormann and Likens, 1967). This fundamental function of each region's ecology is the transfer of nutrients necessary for life from the atmosphere into plants and animals and back again (DeAngelis, 2012). If the organisms that reside in that ecosystem thrive and sustain a consistent population, the nutrient cycle in that habitat must be balanced and stable (McFall-Ngai *et al.*, 2013). Globally, harmful algal blooms are a major environmental issue (Backer, 2002). Harmful algal blooms, such as red tides, blue-green algae, and cyanobacteria, can have

severe consequences for human health, aquatic ecosystems, and the economy (Zohdi and Abbaspour, 2019, Carmichael, 2008, Hallegraeff, 2003, Backer, 2002). Fig. 1 represents the nutrient (Nitrogen/Phosphorous) cycle; nutrients circulate in the atmosphere; terrestrial and aquatic food webs.

Fig. 1. Presents nutrient (Nitrogen/Phosphorous) cycle, nutrients circulate in the atmosphere; terrestrial and aquatic food webs.

Among the activities named as sources of excess nitrogen and phosphorus include agriculture, where animal manure and chemical fertilizers are not managed well (Vitousek *et al.*, 2009, Nahayo *et al.*, 2016, K. Sakadevan and Nguyen, 2017).

Nevertheless, when plants do not fully utilize these nutrients, they can be lost from the farm fields and negatively impact air and downstream water quality (Schröder *et al.*, 2004). The use of fossil fuels in industry, agriculture, transportation, electric power generation leads to generation and therefore increased nitrogen in the air (Akorede *et al.*, 2012, Cui *et al.*, 2013).

On the other hand, stormwater contributes to nutrient pollution as precipitation falls on our cities and towns; it runs across hard surfaces such as roads, rooftops and sidewalks and washout pollutants, including phosphorus and nitrogen, into local watercourses (Marsalek *et al.*, 2008, Grant, 2020, Joshi, 2010). Fig. 2 describes potential sources and effects of nutrient pollution in the environment.

Fig. 2. Describes potential sources and effects of nutrient pollution in the environment, including unclear contribution from stormwater currently not regulated in Sub-Saharan Africa; Nutrients loads from atmospheric deposition; agricultural practices; wastewater treatment plants, and disinfection by-products increases nutrients pollution in the environments leading to non-resilient ecology.

Sewerage and septic systems are responsible for treating large quantities of wastewater. These systems do not continuously operate properly or remove enough nitrogen and phosphorus before discharging into waterways; therefore, wastewater released to the environment carries these nutrients (Cherotich *et al.*, 2021, Egor *et al.*, 2014, Banadda *et al.*, 2009). The presence of hard surfaces and landscaping can further enhance nitrogen and phosphorus run-off and thus nutrient pollution during wet weather (Grant, 2020, Schröder *et al.*, 2004, Sanseverino *et al.*, 2016, Li and Health, 2020). In this case, animal waste contributes excess nutrients to waterways, including certain soaps, detergents that contain nitrogen and phosphorus (Li *et al.*, 2010, Peng *et al.*, 2021). Information on the contribution of nutrient pollution on the presence and growth of diseases causing organisms in the environment is not clear. This study investigates the status of nutrient pollution in Sub Saharan Africa, the potential source of nutrient pollution, the reported effects of nutrient pollution; How to overcome nutrient pollution in the environment.

Global Reports of Nutrient Pollution and their Effects Reports of nutrient pollution are globally available, evidenced by eutrophication (Bai *et al.*, 2018, Wang *et al.*, 2018). For example, in China, 31% of the rivers

and six among nine central coastal bays have suffered from eutrophication as a result of elevated concentrations of phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) (Bai *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, more than 60% of the monitored drinking water wells are severely contaminated (Gu *et al.*, 2013). Further, transfers of N and P from agriculture are the main contributors to the poor water quality (Su *et al.*, 2021, Zhang *et al.*, 2020). According to US EPA, anthropogenic activities cause excessive enrichment of nutrients such as nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) in water bodies. They are currently the utmost prevalent environmental problem facing the United States (Dubey and Dutta, 2020, Bhagowati *et al.*, 2019). The primary point sources of nutrients include watersheds, municipal and industrial wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) (P. A. G. M. Scheren *et al.*, 2000, LYIMO, 2009, D. Dabya, 2002). The wastewater plants lacking design for removal of nutrients contributes much to pollution (Asteggiante and Geis, 2013, Bashar, 2018, Rahman *et al.*, 2016). Apart from other effects, reports of nutrient pollution results in a non-resilient ecosystem are available. That amplified by rapid population growth that primarily cause of worsening water quality, which results in increased inputs from WWTPs, rainwater run-off, and agricultural return flow (Adams *et al.*, 2020).

With phytoplankton blooms (>20 g l⁻¹) and bottom-water hypoxia, the Sundays and Swartkops Estuaries in South Africa are eutrophic (Adams *et al.*, 2020). As a result of WWTPs inputs and high water residence times, the nationally significant Knysna Estuary experiences eutrophic conditions associated with macroalgal blooms. In contrast, the Wildevolvlei and Zeekoe systems have transitioned to alternate stable states characterized by toxic cyanobacteria blooms (Adams *et al.*, 2020). Agricultural inputs from the Umfolozi system are threatening the health of the St Lucia Estuary, a UNESCO World Heritage site indicating the need for mitigation measures (Adams *et al.*, 2020). A study by Alex and Colleagues reported higher NO₃⁻ pollution in the wet season, which may be due to rainfall which accelerated the surface run-off that collects different materials from various

settings into the groundwater sources, including nutrients. Hydrochemical techniques revealed that most nitrates originated from sewage effluents and organic wastes such as manure (Alex *et al.*, 2021). The output of various simulations on nutrients and other contaminants resulting from agronomic practices in farm plots practising cabbage and chrysanthemum cultivation revealed that most contaminants such as pesticides are from fertilizers and not leached beyond the top 10 cm layer. They indicate that excessive fertilizers can cause nitrate contamination to the groundwater in Cameron highlands.

Conversely, Degregori and Colleagues reported that eutrophication affects gut microbiomes of fish (*Stegastes nigricans*) (Degregori *et al.*, 2021). The results of 16S RNA sequencing studies further revealed, hindgut and foregut microbiomes of *S. nigricans* had more alpha diversity than unenriched controls (Degregori *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the gut microbiomes of *S. nigricans* differed significantly between treatments (Degregori *et al.*, 2021). These changes were not observed in the microbiomes of the turf algae consumed by *S. nigricans*, indicating that the gut microbiome changes were autochthonous. In combination, these results provide a novel example of endogenous microbial shifts in wild vertebrates caused by simulated anthropogenic stress (Degregori *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the implementation of nutrient pollution mitigation strategies is essential for the sustainability of the ecosystem.

Status of Nutrient Pollution in Sub-Saharan African Environments

Mangroves are one of the most prolific coastal ecosystems, but they are vulnerable to anthropogenic pollution because of their location at the land-sea interface. Lugendo and Kimei studied anthropogenic contamination in five Tanzanian mangrove ecosystems, comprising non-polluted (Mbegan and Ras Dege), one moderately polluted (Kunduchi), and two contaminated (Mzinga and Kizinga) sites (Lugendo and Kimirei, 2021). The use of stable ¹⁵N isotopes to assess the suitability of mangrove leaves, roots, sediment, and gastropods as indicators of

anthropogenic nitrogen pollution (Lugendo and Kimirei, 2021). The enrichment of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ increased from non-polluted < moderate < polluted (Lugendo and Kimirei, 2021). Polluted areas fed by freshwater streams, likely to absorb significant loads from residential sewage from adjacent settlements and industrial and agricultural effluents (Lugendo and Kimirei, 2021). This study further proposed mangrove leaves, aerial roots, sediment, and gastropod (*T. palustris*) can reliably use as nitrogen pollution indicators. Marine contamination along

Kenyan Coast is claimed to originate from land (Okuku *et al.*, 2019). A decade pollution survey (2008 -2018) to determine the levels of various pollutants, including nutrients in biota collected from selected locations, sediment and water in Kenya was done (Okuku *et al.*, 2019). Results indicates the need for continuous monitoring to protect both ecosystem and human health (Okuku *et al.*, 2019). Table 1 presents the occurrences and distribution of quantitative levels of nutrients in different matrices in Sub Saharan African environments.

Table 1. Occurrence and Distribution of Quantitative levels of Nutrients in Different Matrices in Sub- Saharan Africa Environments.

Country	Nutrient	Concentrations	Matrix	Study period	Source	References	
Kenya	PO ₄ ³⁻ -P	<0.10 - 1560.00 µg/L	Seawater	2019	Anthropogenic from the mainland to marine	(Okuku <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	
	(NO ₂ ⁻ + NO ₃ ⁻)-N	<0.10 -1320.00 µg/L					
	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	<0.10 -3280.00 µg/L					
	Phosphates	0.022-0.039mg/L	Stream water	2021	Anthropogenic pollution Reservoir and potential source if sediments are resuspended	(Cherotich <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	
	Nitrates	0.038-0.163mg/L					
	Ammonium	0.034-0.118mg/L	Sediments	2018-2019	Anthropogenic activities	(Kaimba <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	
	Phosphates	0.217-1.131mg/L					
	Nitrates	0.199-0.603mg/L					
	Ammonium	9.394-26.73mg/L					
	Tanzania	Orthophosphate concentrations	0.326, to 0.422 and 0.524 mg/L	Coral reef	2018-2019		(Kaimba <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Ammonia		<0.1 to 6.0 µgN/L	Lake water	March 2008 to December 2020.	Anthropogenic activities	(Walumona <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	
Nitrate		5 to >150 µgN/L					
Phosphate		15 to >900 µgP/L					
Tanzania			16.44 mg L ⁻¹	mangrove leaves, roots, sediment	2021	Anthropogenic inputs > 10‰ $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values	(Lugendo and Kimirei, 2021)
		Nitrogen	Ranged from 1.1 to 357.7 mg-NO ₃ /l	Wastewater	2018	Anthropogenic activities	(Pantaleo <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
		Nitrite	0.0- 20 µ/mol	coastal beach waters	2008-2009	Anthropogenic activities	(LYIMO, 2009)
		Nitrate	0.2 - 54µ/mol				
		Phosphate	0.3 - 45 µ/mol				
			The concentrations of NO ₃ ⁻	ranged from 2.4 ppm to 929.6 ppm during the dry season and from 2.4 ppm to 1620.0 ppm during the wet season	boreholes, shallow wells	2017-2018	Anthropogenic activities
		Total phosphate	0.26 to 0.54 mg/l	River water	2018	Anthropogenic activities	(Malale <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
	Total nitrogen	0.8 to 1.71 mg/l					
	Total nitrogen	1,472.20 ± 97.52 µg TN L ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹					
	Total phosphate	143.69 ± 4.98 PO ₄ -P L ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹				(Shayo <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	

Country	Nutrient	Concentrations	Matrix	Study period	Source	References	
Uganda	Nitrogen	0 – 2.8 mg L ⁻¹	water	2019 - 2020	Anthropogenic activities	(Turyahabwe <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	
	Phosphorus	mg L ⁻¹					
	Total phosphorous	214 mg L ⁻¹	Wastewater	2018	Anthropogenic activities	(McCord <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	
	Total Kjeldahl nitrogen	1467 mg L ⁻¹					
	Uganda	Nitrogen and Phosphorus	Wastewater and pit latrines lost approximately 2 - 20% of total N and less than 1% of total P mass input to groundwater	Groundwater	2012 - 2013	Anthropogenic activities	(Nyenje <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
		Phosphorus	74%	er flow lines			
Phosphorus		83%	Wastewater	2015	Anthropogenic activities	(Bateganya <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	
Nitrate		0.233-0.577 µg ml ⁻¹	Wastewater	2014	Anthropogenic activities	(Egor <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	
PO ₄ -P NH ₃ -N NO ₃ -N		0.02 mg/l to 19.3 mg/l 0 to 2.36 mg/l 1.8 mg/l to 314.4 mg/l	Wastewater	2011	Anthropogenic activities	(G Wali <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	
Rwanda	Total nitrogen	Influent 64.78 to effluent 34.61 mg/l	Wastewater	April to September 2019	Anthropogenic pollution	(Theoneste <i>et al.</i>)	
	Total phosphorous	Influent 14.05 to effluent 5.41 mg/l					
	Total nitrogen Total phosphorous	25.43±5.82 mg l ⁻¹ 1.25±0.95 mg l ⁻¹	Fish pond	April to September 2019	Anthropogenic pollution	(Niyotwambaza <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	
S. Sudan	Nitrogen	40 mg L ⁻¹ NH ₃ -N and 5 mg L ⁻¹ NO ₃ -N	Influent	2012	Early initiation and integration of wetlands for removal of nutrients	(Ladu <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	
Cameroon	Nitrate	0.72 – 3.41 mg L ⁻¹	River water	August - October 2012	Anthropogenic pollution	(Khalik <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	
	Phosphate	0.63 – 1.35 mg L ⁻¹					
	Nitrite	0.010 – 0.045 mg L ⁻¹					
	Ammonia	0.07 – 0.19 mg L ⁻¹	Sediments				
Botswana	Nitrate	7 to 10 times higher	River water	June 2008 to June 2010	Anthropogenic pollution	(Gondwe <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	
	Phosphate	0.222 to 0.698 mg L ⁻¹					
	Total nitrogen	0.042 to 0.131 mg L ⁻¹					
Zimbabwe	Nitrogen	13.5 mg/L	River water	June 2000 to December 2001.	Anthropogenic pollution	(Nhapi and Tirivarombo, 2004)	
	Phosphorus	2.6 mg/L					

The practice of releasing raw or partially treated wastewater in urban water bodies makes the issue of nutrient pollution a transboundary effect (Ukwe and Ibe, 2010, Lintern *et al.*, 2020). For example, Guinea current large marine ecosystem stretches from Guinea Bissau to Angola. It encompasses sixteen nations in West and Central Africa and is restricted by different bathymetry, hydrography, chemistry, and trophodynamics, with the Guinea current serving as the unifying characteristic (Ukwe and Ibe, 2010). Pollution from domestic and industrial sources such as nutrient pollution, overfishing, and poorly planned

and managed coastal and offshore developments and near-shore activities have resulted in the rapid degradation of vulnerable inshore and offshore habitats and shared living marine resources, jeopardizing the economies and health of the population (Ukwe and Ibe, 2010). Reports of available treatment schemes in Zambia to be incapable of removing nutrients are available (Sinkala *et al.*, Zgambo, 2003, Alsterhag and Petersson, 2004), leading to nutrient pollution. A similar scenario in Malawi, where nutrient pollution originates from effluents, indicating proper sanitation infrastructure

may help manage nutrient pollution in our environment (León *et al.*, 2003, Hranova *et al.*, 2005). Further reports indicate that in Angola and Namibia, the Okavango River Basin extracts 18.13 per cent of the mean annual flow for urban water supply and irrigates 108,992 hectares of barren Kalahari sandy soils that require high fertilization rates (Vushe, 2019). Indicating the river system's high leaching and, as a result, nutrient pollution (Vushe, 2019, Vushe *et al.*, 2016, Woltersdorf *et al.*, 2016). In most areas affected by nutrient pollution higher contribution is from anthropogenic activities.

Effects of Nutrient pollution

Nutrient pollution may lead to the disruption of vital ecological functions of ecosystems. For example, essential ecosystem functions on coral reefs were altered by nutrient pollution (Silbiger *et al.*, 2018). Reports of water bodies becoming eutrophic are available globally, including sub-Saharan Africa (Nyenje *et al.*, 2010, Ferreira *et al.*, 2015, Adams *et al.*, 2020, Janse and Van Puijenbroek, 1998, Tomascik and Sander, 1987). The rate of water bodies becoming eutrophic is projected to increase as anthropogenic activities increases leading to increased nutrient pollution. Such activities include animal farming to overcome the need for a growing population, modern agricultural practices, and the use of home cleaning agents and detergents containing nutrients (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015, Patricia M. Glibert *et al.*, 2018).

The direct environmental implications of eutrophication include an increase in suspended particles due to widespread macroalgal blooms, a loss in water clarity, and an increase in precipitation rate, which has destroyed benthic habitat due to shade of submerged vegetation (Dorgham, 2014, Janse and Van Puijenbroek, 1998, Tomascik and Sander, 1987, Worm *et al.*, 2006, Tomascik and Sander, 1985).

On the other hand, A 96 hours acute toxicity test to investigate the sensitivity of *Neorpela spio*, *Baetis harrisoni*, and *Tubifex* spp. to phosphates (PO₄-P) and nitrates (NO₃-N) at various concentrations (Elias,

2020). Results revealed the presence of lethal effects, including increased mortality with concentration and exposure time among tested species of different sensitivities (Elias, 2020).

Phosphate and nitrate are toxic to the three studied organisms under the test conditions, with *Neorpela spio* displaying the highest acute effect compared to *Baetis harrisoni* and *Tubifex* spp (Elias, 2020). For *N. spio*, 3.2 mg NO₃-N/L and 2.4 mg PO₄-P/L, 5.6 mg NO₃-N/L and 4.8 mg PO₄-P/L for *B. harrisoni*, and 128 mg NO₃-N/L and 24 mg PO₄-P/L for *T. spp.*, 100 per cent cumulative mortality was observed (Elias, 2020). The Tanzanian nitrate recommended lower and upper limits of 10 and 75 mg NO₃-N/L for drinking water caused higher mortality to *N. spio* and *B. harrisoni*. Significant mortality at the recommended nitrite (20 mg NO₃-N/L) and phosphorus (6 mg PO₄-P/L) concentrations for municipal and industrial wastewaters indicate the need for reformation of policies (Elias, 2020).

Muhando and Coallegues (2013) investigated the distribution and abundance of corallimorpharians (*Cnidaria anthozoa*) in Tanzania with various aspects of the coral reef environment. The results indicated a positive relationship between the per cent cover of corallimorpharians and water turbidity. Corallimorpharians were observed to dominate more disturbed reef areas affected by higher nutrient loads (Christopher A. Muhando *et al.*, 2003). Indicating that nutrient pollution has a significant impact on species distribution and abundance in any ecosystem.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Anthropogenic influences are said to contribute more to nutrient pollution, and a variety of impacts have been listed that lead to non-resilient ecology. There is a greater need for resilient ecosystems. Appropriate waste and wastewater management strategies such as the inclusion removal of nutrients in the design of treatment schemes are required. On the other hand, future management planning should include more sustainable farming methods and enhanced wastewater treatment as a trade-off between economic development and environmental protection.

References

- Adams J, Taljaard S, Van Niekerk L, Lemley DJAJOAS.** 2020. Nutrient Enrichment As A Threat To The Ecological Resilience And Health Of South African Microtidal Estuaries **45**, 23-40.
- Akorede M, Hizam H, Ab Kadir M, Aris I, Buba Sjr, Reviews Se.** 2012. Mitigating The Anthropogenic Global Warming In The Electric Power Industry **16**, 2747-2761.
- Alex R, Kitalika A, Mogusu E, Njau Kjg.** 2021. Sources of Nitrate In Ground Water Aquifers Of The Semiarid Region of Tanzania. 2021.
- Alsterhag E, Petersson L.** 2004. Nutrient Loading In The Kafue River Between Mazabuka And Kafue Town, Zambia. J Uppsala University.
- Assessment Er.** 2003. Overview Of Freshwater And Marine Toxicity Tests: A Technical Tool For.
- Asteggiate, Geis Lg.** 2013. Utilizing Herbicide Degradation Products And Artificial Sweeteners As Stable Tracers To Examine Agricultural And Urban Nutrient Sources Within Two Tributaries Of The Chesapeake Bay.
- Backer L. C.** 2002. Cyanobacterial Harmful Algal Blooms (Cyanohabs): Developing A Public Health Response. J Lake Reservoir Management **18**, 20-31.
- Bai Z, Lu J, Zhao H, Velthof Gl, Oenema O, Chadwick D, Williams Jr, Jin S, Liu H, Wang M.** 2018. Designing Vulnerable Zones Of Nitrogen And Phosphorus Transfers To Control Water Pollution In China. Acs Publications.
- Banadda E, Kansiime F, Kigobe M, Kizza M, Nhapi Ijwp.** 2009. Landuse-Based Nonpoint Source Pollution: A Threat To Water Quality In Murchison Bay, Uganda. J Water Policy **11**, 94-105.
- Bashar R.** 2018. Evaluation Of Phosphorus Removal /Recovery Processes During Municipal Wastewater Treatment, The University Of Wisconsin-Madison.
- Bateganya NL, Nakalanzi D, Babu M, Hein TJET.** 2015. Buffering Municipal Wastewater Pollution Using Urban Wetlands In Sub-Saharan Africa: A Case Of Masaka Municipality, Uganda **36**, 2149-2160.
- Bhagowati B, Ahamad Ku, Hydrobiologyje.** 2019. A Review On Lake Eutrophication Dynamics And Recent Developments In Lake Modeling **19**, 155-166.
- Bormann Fh, Likens Ge.** 1967. Nutrient Cycling. J Science Of The Total Environment **155**, 424-429.
- Camargo J, Ward JJC.** 1992. Short-Term Toxicity Of Sodium Nitrate (Nano₃) To Non-Target Freshwater Invertebrates **24**, 23-28.
- Camargo J, Ward JJC.** 1995. Nitrate (No₃□ N) Toxicity To Aquatic Life: A Proposal Of Safe Concentrations For Two Species Of Nearctic Freshwater Invertebrates **31**, 3211-3216.
- Camargo Ja, Alonso A, Salamanca Ajc.** 2005. Nitrate Toxicity To Aquatic Animals: A Review With New Data For Freshwater Invertebrates **58**, 1255-1267.
- Camargo Ja, Alonso Ájei.** 2006. Ecological And Toxicological Effects Of Inorganic Nitrogen Pollution In Aquatic Ecosystems: A Global Assessment **32**, 831-849.
- Carmichael W.** 2008. A World Overview—One-Hundred-Twenty-Seven Years Of Research On Toxic Cyanobacteria—Where Do We Go From Here? J Cyanobacterial Harmful Algal Blooms: State Of The Science Research Needs 105-125.
- Chadwick Dr, Williams Jr, Lu Y, Ma L, Bai Z, Hou Y, Chen X, Misselbrook Th.** 2020. Strategies To Reduce Nutrient Pollution From Manure Management In China. Frontiers Of Agricultural Science Engineering **7**, 45-55.
- Chen X, Stokal M, Van Vliet Mt, Stuiver J, Wang M, Bai Z, Ma L, Kroeze C.** 2019. Multi-Scale Modeling Of Nutrient Pollution In The Rivers Of China. Environmental Science Technology **53**, 9614-9625.

- Cherotich S, Abong Od, Onyatta JJCSIJ.** 2021. Assessing The Seasonal Changes On Physicochemical Parameters And Major Nutrient Levels In Water And Sediments From Sulal River, Bureti Sub County, Kericho County, Kenya 46-58.
- Christopher A, Muhand O, Baraka L, Kuguru, Gregory M, Wagner, Mbije Ne, Ohman MC.** 2003. Environmental Effects On The Distribution Of Corallimorpharians In Tanzania. *Ambio Journal Of Human Environment*.
- Council Nr.** 1992. Restoration Of Aquatic Ecosystems: Science, Technology, And Public Policy, National Academies Press.
- Cui S, Shi Y, Groffman Pm, Schlesinger Wh, Zhu Gjpotnaos Y.** 2013. Centennial-Scale Analysis Of The Creation And Fate Of Reactive Nitrogen In China (1910-2010) **110**, 2052-2057.
- Dabya Jt, Jagob C.** 2002. Microbial And Nutrient Pollution Of Coastal Bathing Waters In Mauritius. *Environment International* **27**, 555-566.
- Daily G.** 2003. What Are Ecosystem Services. *J Global Environmental Challenges For The Twenty-First Century: Resources, Consumption Sustainable Solutions* 227-231.
- Deangelis Dl.** 2012. Dynamics Of Nutrient Cycling And Food Webs, Springer Science & Business Media.
- Degregori S, Casey Jm, Barber Phjmb.** 2021. Nutrient Pollution Alters The Gut Microbiome Of A Territorial Reef Fish. *J Marine Pollution Bulletin* **169**, 112522.
- Dorgham MM.** 2014. Effects Of Eutrophication. *Eutrophication: Causes, Consequences And Control*. Springer.
- Dubey D, Dutta V.** 2020. Nutrient Enrichment In Lake Ecosystem And Its Effects On Algae And Macrophytes. *Environmental Concerns And Sustainable Development*. Springer.
- Egor M, Mbabazi J, Ntale Mjijocm, Research E.** 2014. Heavy Metal And Nutrient Loading Of River Rwizi By Effluents From Mbarara Municipality, Western Uganda **2**, 36-47.
- Elias JDJIJOE.** 2020. Response Of Tropical African Macroinvertebrates With Varying Tolerances To Different Levels Of Nitrate And Phosphate. *J International Journal Of Ecology* 2020.
- Ferreira V, Castagneyrol B, Koricheva J, Gulis V, Chauvet E, Graça Ma.** 2015. A Meta-Analysis Of The Effects Of Nutrient Enrichment On Litter Decomposition In Streams. *J Biological Reviews* **90**, 669-688.
- Gwali U, Nhapi I, Ngombwa A, Banadda N, Nsengimana Hj, Kimwaga R, Nansubuga JIJOEEJ.** 2011. Modelling Of Nonpoint Source Pollution In Akagera Transboundary River In Rwanda 4.
- Gondwe MJ, Masamba W, Murray-Hudson M.** 2017. Water Balance And Variations Of Nutrients And Major Solutes Along A River Transect Through The Okavango Delta, Botswana. *J Botswana Notes Records* **49**, 26-43.
- Grant VA.** 2020. Water Quality Of Stormwater Runoff Into Lake Wānaka, New Zealand. University Of Otago.
- Gu B, Ge Y, Chang Sx, Luo W, Chang JJGEC.** 2013. Nitrate In Groundwater Of China: Sources And Driving Forces **23**, 1112-1121.
- Hallegraeff G.** 2003. Harmful Algal Blooms: A Global Overview. *J Manual On Harmful Marine Microalgae* **33**, 1-22.
- Hranova R, Nkambule S, Mwandira S.** 2005. Diffuse Pollution Of Urban Rivers—Case Studies In Malawi And Swaziland. *Diffuse Pollution Of Water Resources*. Crc Press.
- Janse Jh, Van Puijenbroek PJ.** 1998. Effects Of Eutrophication In Drainage Ditches. *Nitrogen, The Confer-Ns*. Elsevier.

- Joshi UM.** 2010. Chemical Contaminants In Urban Runoff: Characteristics, Sources And Low Cost Treatment.
- Sakadevan K, Nguyen ML.** 2017. Livestock Production And Its Impact On Nutrient Pollution And Greenhouse Gas Emissions. *Advances In Agronomy* 141.
- Kaimba A, De, Villiers S, Wambua SJFIES.** 2019. Does Protection Of Marine Areas Safeguard Coral Reefs From Human-Source Pollution? 7, 89.
- Khalik W, Abdullah M, Padli N, Amerudin N.** 2013. Assessment On Nutrient Status In Water And Sediment Quality Of Bertam River, Cameron Highlands. *J International Journal Of Chemical Sciences* 11, 709-720.
- Kuwayama Y, Olmstead Sm, Wietelman Dc, Zheng J.** 2020. Trends In Nutrient-Related Pollution As A Source Of Potential Water Quality Damages: A Case Study Of Texas, Usa. *Science Of The Total Environment* 724, 137962.
- Ladu Jlc, Loboka Mk, Lukaw YS.** 2012. Integrated Constructed Wetland For Nitrogen Elimination From Domestic Sewage: The Case Study Of Soba Rural Area In Khartoum South, Sudan. *J Natural Science* 10, 30-36.
- Lapointe BE, Herren LW, Paule AL.** 2017. Septic Systems Contribute To Nutrient Pollution And Harmful Algal Blooms In The St. Lucie Estuary, Southeast Florida, Usa. *Harmful Algae* 70, 1-22.
- Leip A, Billen G, Garnier J, Grizzetti B, Lassaletta L, Reis S, Simpson D, Sutton Ma, De Vries W, Weiss Fjerl.** 2015. Impacts Of European Livestock Production: Nitrogen, Sulphur, Phosphorus And Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Land-Use, Water Eutrophication And Biodiversity 10, 115004.
- León LF, Lam D, Mccrimmon C, Swayne DA.** 2003. Watershed Management Modelling In Malawi: Application And Technology Transfer. *J Environmental Modelling Software* 18, 531-539.
- Li PJ, Health E.** 2020. To Make The Water Safer 1-6.
- Li S, Yuan Z, Bi J, Wu HJSOTTE.** 2010. Anthropogenic Phosphorus Flow Analysis Of Hefei City, China. *J Science Of The Total Environment* 408, 5715-5722.
- Lintern A, Mcphillips L, Winfrey B, Duncan J, Grady C.** 2020. Best Management Practices For Diffuse Nutrient Pollution: Wicked Problems Across Urban And Agricultural Watersheds. *J Environmental Science Technology* 54, 9159-9174.
- Lugendo BR, Kimirei IA.** 2021. Anthropogenic Nitrogen Pollution In Mangrove Ecosystems Along Dar Es Salaam And Bagamoyo Coasts In Tanzania. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 168, 112415.
- Lyimo TJ.** 2009. Microbial And Nutrient Pollution In The Coastal Bathing Waters Of Dar Es Salaam. *Aquatic Conserv: Mar. Freshw. Ecosyst* 19, S27-S37.
- Malale M, Subira MJT, Technology JOE.** 2018. Surface Water Quality In Peri-Urban Areas In Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania: The Case Of Ng'ombe River 37.
- Marsalek J, Cisneros BJ, Karamouz M, Malmquist PA, Goldenfum JA, Chocat B.** 2008. Urban Water Cycle Processes And Interactions: Urban Water Series-Unesco-Ihp, Crc Press.
- Mccord A, Stefanos S, Tumwesige V, Lsoto D, Kawala M, Mutebi J, Nansubuga I, Larson Rjra, Systems F.** 2020. Anaerobic Digestion In Uganda: Risks And Opportunities For Integration Of Waste Management And Agricultural Systems 35, 678-687.
- Mcfall-Ngai M, Hadfield MG, Bosch TC, Carey HV, Domazet-Lošo T, Douglas AE, Dubilier N, Eberl G, Fukami T, Gilbert SF.** 2013. Animals In A Bacterial World, A New Imperative For The Life Sciences. *J Proceedings Of The National Academy Of Sciences* 110, 3229-3236.
- Nahayo L, Li L, Kayiranga A, Karamage F, Mupenzi C, Ndayisaba F, Nyesheja Emjajoar.** 2016. Agricultural Impact On Environment And Counter Measures In Rwanda 11, 2205-2212.

- Nhapi I, Tirivarombo S.** 2004. Sewage Discharges And Nutrient Levels In Marimba River, Zimbabwe. *J Water Sanitation-Related Diseases The Changing Environment* **30**, 107-113.
- Niyotwambaza Ch, Nhapi I, Wali UG, Tabaro SR.** 2010. Nutrient Distribution In A Fish Pond At Rwasave Fish Farming And Research Station, Rwanda. *J Rwanda Journal* **21**, 29-49.
- Nyenje P, Foppen J, Uhlenbrook S, Kulabako R, Muwanga AJSOTTE.** 2010. Eutrophication And Nutrient Release In Urban Areas Of Sub-Saharan Africa—A Review **408**, 447-455.
- Nyenje PM, Foppen JW, Kulabako R, Muwanga A, Uhlenbrook S.** 2013. Nutrient Pollution In Shallow Aquifers Underlying Pit Latrines And Domestic Solid Waste Dumps In Urban Slums. *J Environ Manage* **122**, 15-24.
- Okuku EO, Imbayi KL, Omondi OG, Wayayi WVO, Sezi MC, Maureen KM, Mwangi S, Oduor N.** 2019. Decadal Pollution Assessment And Monitoring Along The Kenya Coast. *Monitoring Of Marine Pollution*. Intechopen.
- Orians GH, Milewski Avj BR.** 2007. Ecology Of Australia: The Effects Of Nutrient-Poor Soils And Intense Fires. *J Biological Reviews* **82**, 393-423.
- Scheren Pagm, Zanting Ha, Lemmens Amc.** 2000. Estimation Of Water Pollution Sources In Lake Victoria, East Africa: Application And Elaboration Of The Rapid Assessment Methodology. *Journal Of Environmental Management* **58**, 235-248.
- Pantaleo P, Komakech HC, Mtei KM, Njau KNJWP.** 2018. Contamination Of Groundwater Sources In Emerging African Towns: The Case Of Babati Town, Tanzania. *J Water Practice Technology* **13**, 980-990.
- Patricia M, Glibert, Arthur Hw, Beusen, John A, Harrison, Hans H, D'Urr, Alexander F, Bouwman, Laruelle GG.** 2018. Changing Land-, Sea-, And Airscapes: Sources Of Nutrient Pollution Affecting Habitat Suitability For Harmful Algae. *Changing Land-, Sea-, And Airspaces*.
- Peng Z, Ma X, Chen X, Coyte Pejes, Research P.** 2021. The Impacts Of Pollution And Its Associated Spatial Spillover Effects On Ill-Health In China 1-10.
- Rahman SM, Eckelman MJ, Onnis-Hayden A, Gu AZ.** 2016. Life-Cycle Assessment Of Advanced Nutrient Removal Technologies For Wastewater Treatment. *J Environmental Science Technology* **50**, 3020-3030.
- Sanseverino I, Conduto D, Pozzoli L, Dobricic S, Lettieri TJEC.** 2016. Joint Research Centre Institute For Environment & Sustainability 2016. *Algal Bloom And Its Economic Impact*.
- Schröder J, Scholefield D, Cabral F, Hofman Gjes, Policy.** 2004. The Effects Of Nutrient Losses From Agriculture On Ground And Surface Water Quality: The Position Of Science In Developing Indicators For Regulation **7**, 15-23.
- Selman M, Greenhalgh SJRRJ.** 2010. Eutrophication: Sources And Drivers Of Nutrient Pollution. *J Renewable Resources Journal* **26**, 19-26.
- Shaviv A, Mikkelsen RJFR.** 1993. Controlled-Release Fertilizers To Increase Efficiency Of Nutrient Use And Minimize Environmental Degradation-A Review **35**, 1-12.
- Shayo S, Limbu Smjl, Research R, Management.** 2018. Nutrient Release From Sediments And Biological Nitrogen Fixation: Advancing Our Understanding Of Eutrophication Sources In Lake Victoria, Tanzania **23**, 312-323.
- Silbiger NJ, Nelson CE, Remple K, Sevilla JK, Quinlan ZA, Putnam Hm, Fox MD, Donahue MJ.** 2018. Nutrient Pollution Disrupts Key Ecosystem Functions On Coral Reefs. *J Proceedings Of The Royal Society* **285**, 20172718.
- Sinkala T, Mwala M, Mwase E.** Application Of Pollutant Reduction And Weed Utilization As Management Measures For Aquatic Weeds In The Lower Kafue River, Zambia.

- Su H, Kang W, Li Y, Li ZJEP.** 2021. Fluoride And Nitrate Contamination Of Groundwater In The Loess Plateau, China: Sources And Related Human Health Risks **286**, 117287.
- Theoneste S, Vincent Nm, Xavier NF.** The Effluent Quality Discharged And Its Impacts On The Receiving Environment Case Of Kacyiru Sewerage Treatment Plant, Kigali, Rwanda.
- Tomascik T, Sander FJMB.** 1985. Effects Of Eutrophication On Reef-Building Corals **87**, 143-155.
- Tomascik T, Sander FJMB.** 1987. Effects Of Eutrophication On Reef-Building Corals **94**, 53-75.
- Turyahabwe R, Mulinya C, Shivoga WA.** 2020. Influence Of Land Use/Cover On Water Quality In The River Sironko Catchment Area, Eastern Uganda.
- Ukwe C, Ibe C.** 2010. A Regional Collaborative Approach In Transboundary Pollution Management In The Guinea Current Region Of Western Africa. J Ocean Coastal Management **53**, 493-506.
- Vitousek PM, Naylor R, Crews T, David MB, Drinkwater L, Holland E, Johnes P, Katzenberger J, Martinelli L, Matson PJS.** 2009. Nutrient Imbalances In Agricultural Development **324**, 1519-1520.
- Vushe A.** 2019. Nitrate-Nitrogen Pollution And Attenuation Upstream Of The Okavango Delta In Angola And Namibia. Agriculture And Ecosystem Resilience In Sub Saharan Africa. Springer.
- Vushe A, Von Landsberg L, Groengroeft A, Mashauri DA.** 2016. Nitrate Leaching In Irrigated Inorganic Agriculture: A Case Study Of Mashare Commercial Farm In Namibia, Okavango River Basin. J African Journal Of Agricultural Research **11**, 2871-2881.
- Walumona JR, Odoli CO, Raburu P, Amisi FM, Murakaru MJ, Kondowe BN, Kaunda-Arara BJJ, Research R.** 2021. Spatio-Temporal Variations In Selected Water Quality Parameters And Trophic Status Of Lake Baringo, Kenya **26**, E12367.
- Wang M, Ma L, Strokhal M, Ma W, Liu X, Kroeze CJES.** 2018. Hotspots For Nitrogen And Phosphorus Losses From Food Production In China: A County-Scale Analysis **52**, 5782-5791.
- Woltersdorf L, Scheidegger R, Liehr S, Döll P.** 2016. Municipal Water Reuse For Urban Agriculture In Namibia: Modeling Nutrient And Salt Flows As Impacted By Sanitation User Behavior. J Journal Of Environmental Management **169**, 272-284.
- Worm B, Lotze HKJL.** 2006. Effects Of Eutrophication, Grazing, And Algal Blooms On Rocky Shores **51**, 569-579.
- Zgambo A.** 2003. An Investigation Of The Amount And Environmental Impact Of Chemical Fertilizers And Pesticides Running Off From Commercial And Traditional Farmlands In The Upper Kaleyia Catchment, Mazabuka, Zambia.
- Zhang H, Xu Y, Cheng S, Li Q, Yu HJSOTTE.** 2020. Application Of The Dual-Isotope Approach And Bayesian Isotope Mixing Model To Identify Nitrate In Groundwater Of A Multiple Land-Use Area In Chengdu Plain, China **717**, 137134.
- Zohdi E, Abbaspour M.** 2019. Harmful Algal Blooms (Red Tide): A Review Of Causes, Impacts And Approaches To Monitoring And Prediction. J International Journal Of Environmental Science Technology **16**, 1789-1806.